

THE ROLE OF CRITICAL THINKING IN MODERN EDUCATION AND HOW TO IMPROVE IT

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Abstract. Critical thinking is a fundamental cognitive skill that enables individuals to analyze information objectively and make well-reasoned decisions. This study examines the significance of critical thinking in enhancing independent thinking, problem-solving abilities promoting intellectual abilities, and also facilitating informed decision-making within educational contexts. By emphasizing cognitive skill development, critical thinking equips students with essential tools for academic success and lifelong learning. Its integration into educational sphere ensures that learners not only acquire knowledge but also develop the capacity to apply it effectively in real-life situations. It can be developed through several key academic practices, extensive reading, and constructive feedback.

Key words: critical thinking, education, problem-solving, decision-making, lifelong learning, integration into education, intellectual abilities, constructive feedback.

Annotatsiya

Tanqidiy fikrlash — bu ma'lumotlarni xolisona tahlil qilish va asosli qarorlar qabul qilish imkonini beruvchi fundamental kognitiv ko'nikmadir. Ushbu tadqiqot ta'lim jarayonida tanqidiy fikrlashning mustaqil fikrlashni shakllantirish, muammolarni hal qilish qobiliyatini oshirish, intellektual salohiyatni yuksaltirish va ongli qarorlar qabul qilishdagi ahamiyatini o'rganadi. Tanqidiy fikrlash kognitiv ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishga e'tibor qaratgan holda, talabalarni akademik muvaffaqiyat va hayot davomida bilim olish uchun zarur vositalar bilan qurollantiradi. Uni ta'lim sohasiga integratsiya qilish o'quvchilarning nafaqat bilim olishini, balki ushbu bilimlarni real hayotiy vaziyatlarda samarali qo'llash qobiliyatini rivojlantirishini ham ta'minlaydi. Mazkur ko'nikma keng ko'lamli mutolaa, konstruktiv fikr-mulohazalar va bir qator akademik amaliyotlar orqali shakllantirilishi mumkin.

Tayanch so'zlar: tanqidiy fikrlash, ta'lim, muammolarni hal qilish, qaror qabul qilish, hayot davomida bilim olish, ta'limga integratsiya, intellektual qobiliyatlar, konstruktiv aloqa.

Аннотация. Критическое мышление является фундаментальным когнитивным навыком, позволяющим объективно анализировать информацию и принимать обоснованные решения. В данном исследовании рассматривается значение критического мышления в развитии независимого мышления, способности к решению проблем, повышении интеллектуальных способностей, а также в содействии принятию обоснованных решений в образовательном контексте. Делая акцент на развитии когнитивных навыков, критическое мышление вооружает студентов инструментами, необходимыми для академического успеха и обучения на протяжении всей жизни. Его интеграция в

образовательную сферу гарантирует, что учащиеся не только приобретают знания, но и развивают способность эффективно применять их в реальных жизненных ситуациях. Данный навык может быть развит посредством ключевых академических практик, обширного чтения и конструктивной обратной связи.

Ключевые слова: критическое мышление, образование, решение проблем, принятие решений, обучение на протяжении всей жизни, интеграция в образование, интеллектуальные способности, конструктивная обратная связь.

Critical thinking is widely recognized as a cornerstone of modern education due to its ability to transform passive learning into active engagement. In today's digital age, learners are bombarded with information from countless resources. This skill helps them find credible sources, question assumptions, how to use it effectively and make informed judgments. Educational systems strive to cultivate well-rounded individuals, integrating critical thinking into curricula has become essential for fostering independence.[1] Furthermore, rather than mere memorizing information, students with critical thinking abilities can evaluate, interpret and synthesize knowledge in a various and meaningful ways. For example, in a history class, rather than just memorizing dates and events which is useful way to learn, students examine the causes and consequences of conflicts, compare different perspectives, and assess the reliability of sources. This approach enables learners to understand deeper connections, apply their gained knowledge.

Developing independent judgment strengthens student capacity to make informed and strategic decisions. Through critical evaluation and careful consideration of alternative perspectives, learners enhances their reflective reasoning and analytical skills. This cultivation of autonomy prepares them to navigate complex challenges effectively, improving intellectual maturity and ensuring their readiness for academic, professional and societal responsibilities[2]

This valuable skill also significantly improves problem-solving skills, which are essential for academic success and future professional challenges. Real-world problems are rarely straightforward. By analyzing it systematically, students can identify underlying causes, evaluate alternative solutions and select the most effective solution. In scientific research or mathematical problem sets, for instance, critical thinkers can easily detect inconsistencies, test hypothesis and make logical, relevant inference that lead to accurate conclusions. Therefore, problem-solving becomes a transferable skill applicable in unfamiliar or real contexts.[2]

When a student is trained to think critically, they can develop insatiable curiosity about the world them without variety problems. This curiosity motivates them to actively examines and interpret information and experiences. They generate their own ideas, evaluate everything that related to education, as a result of this skill, which boosts creativity. All critical thinkers will experiment with creativity during their lifestyle compared to others.[3]

Considering its significant impact on student's intellectual and personal improvement, it becomes necessary to explore practical ways of cultivating and strengthening critical thinking skills. developing it requires a structured and continuous approach.. First and foremost, attending actively in debates or talk to more people can boost critical thinking. Discussions or debates in classrooms can involve a wide range of ideas, asking questions, and challenging assumptions. If learners attend consistently in there, they can learn how to articulate ideas, listen to different perspectives, analyze

it, respond to alternatives and finally evaluate arguments, which strengths thinking and communication skills.

Reading has a important role in the development of this skill, as it actively engages the mind analysis and evaluation. Through exposure of contexts -ranging from simple ones to academic- enables them to interrogate divergent viewpoints and deconstruct complex arguments with greater intellectual precision. Instead of accepting passively, learners are prompted to scrutinize validity, coherence. Ultimately it nurtures a more discerning and intellectual autonomous thinker.[3]

Finally seeking feedback from highly-competent ones or peers is an indispensable part of improving critical thinking skills. Feedback encourages to reflect on their performances, identify weaknesses, refine their reasoning processes. when they constructive feedback ,they are prompted to move beyond surface-level understanding and engage in deeper self-evaluation of their arguments. Importantly, students should also be open to it, and be willing to revise their ideas based on feedback.

Conclusion. This study shows that integration of critical thinking within educational contexts plays a pivotal role in education through analytical reasoning, fostering independent thinking, problem-solving skills and decision making. Deliberate integration of this skill into educational curricula ensures not only improves learning outcomes but also the preparation of adaptable, competent and innovative individuals for lifelong personal and general growth. This skill can be effectively developed through consistent encouragement, active participation in discussions, and regular use of feedback.

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